

Financial transmission channels of the Polycrisis in the EU (No. 5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007)

Version 1

Description

The overarching aim of the project is to conceptualize the financial transmission channels of the polycrisis in the EU. In doing so, the project intends to produce high-impact, policy-relevant research outputs.

Funder

European Commission | EC

Grant

EU Recovery and Resilience
Facility project "Internal and
External Consolidation of the
University of Latvia" (No.
5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007)

Researchers

Leonardo Pataccini (0000-0002-8436-1596)

Organizations
University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Financial transmission channels of the Polycrisis in the EU (No. 5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007)

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Organizations:

University of Latvia

Contact: Pataccini Leonardo (leonardo@lu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Commission | EC

Grants: EU Recovery and Resilience Facility project "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia" (No. 5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007)

Project: Financial transmission channels of the Polycrisis in the EU

3. License

License:

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date:

4. Templates

Descriptions

Financial transmission channels of the Polycrisis in the EU

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Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Aggregate data
- Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- PDF
- CSV
- XLS
- Others

DOC

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Data from publicly available statistical databases will be reused.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Researchers and students in the field of international political economy.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

No

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Microsoft Office package, Gephi

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Attribution Assurance Licenses

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2027-01-01

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

The project has no additional funding for this aim.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

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3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

There will not be funding for this aim.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Encryption
- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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